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of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

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Enduring with Heaven as My Companion

From the moment my innocent mind awoke,
I was thrown into the trials of this world
Into burdens I was never meant to carry,
For people can be cruel
And hearts can be deceiving.

Wrong turns, dark choices, forbidden paths
Life and fate placed them before me.
I was judged, condemned,
Made into a shame in the eyes of society,
Yet I rose again from the ruins,
Still striving to climb beyond my suffering.

It is not yet the end of everything
Words that many cling to in despair.
I am only human, a soul that stumbled,
Led astray by temptation,
But never truly defeated.

And so I continue to dream,
Dreaming of a life beyond poverty's chains.
I endure every hardship in silence,
For Heaven is the hope I carry within me.

I am not evil.
I am not a failure.
I am merely human
A man once blinded by temptation.
Yet I endure,
Because my eyes are fixed upon Heaven,
For within that promised light
Lies the truest form of happiness,
Even when reached
Through suffering and sacrifice.